

Regeneration of aldehydes from oximes, semicarbazones, phenylhydrazones and tosylhydrazones using phosphorus pentoxide in solvent-free condition under microwave irradiation

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Manuscript received 9 September 2002, accepted 12 December 2002

Microwave irradiation on oximes, semicarbazones, phenylhydrazones and tosylhydrazones of various aldehydes, using phosphorus pentoxide in solvent-free condition provides a fast, efficient and simple method for regeneration of aldehydes in fair to excellent yields.

There has been considerable interest in the development of methods for the regeneration of aldehydes from stable and readily prepared oximes, semicarbazones, phenylhydrazones and tosylhydrazones. These aldehyde derivatives are not only extensively used for characterization and purification of the aldehydes, but also useful as protecting groups¹ in multistep synthesis, as aldehydes are reactive towards a large number of reagents. So, deprotection² is also very much needed, when it is required. Although quite a large number of reagents for the regeneration of ketones³⁻²⁰ from their derivatives are known, the number is limited for the regeneration of aldehydes²¹⁻²⁹. Some of the reagents, which regenerate ketones successfully, are not applicable for regeneration of aldehydes, as they either produce aldehyde in low yield or furnish a complex mixture of products^{9-10,13,15,19,20}. Besides, some of the reagents, viz.

thallium(III)^{21,22}, lead(IV)²³, chromium(VI)²⁹, which regenerate aldehydes, are toxic metal compounds. So the discovery of new, efficient, fast, easily available, inexpensive reagent for the regeneration of aldehydes from their derivatives is the goal of the chemists.

In recent years, the growing interest in the application of microwave radiation³⁰ in chemical reaction enhancement is due to high reaction rates and formation of cleaner products. The solvent-free reactions³¹ under this condition are especially appealing for providing an eco-friendly system. In continuation of our ongoing programme³² to develop synthetic protocols utilizing microwave radiation under solvent-free condition, herein we report the regeneration of aldehydes in fair to excellent yields and in short time from oximes, semicarbazones, phenylhydrazones and tosylhy-

Table 1. Regeneration of aldehydes from various derivatives using phosphorus pentoxide under microwave irradiation

Sl. no.	Aldehydes ^a	From							
		Oximes		Semicarbazones		Phenylhydrazones		Tosylhydrazones	
		Time	Yield	Time	Yield	Time	Yield	Time	Yield
		s	%	s	%	s	%	s	%
1.	Anisaldehyde	40	90	120	90	31	85	50	88
2.	4-Nitrobenzaldehyde	40	75	80	75	40	78	40	73
3.	Veratraldehyde	40	72	40	78	80	90	40	72
4.	Piperonal	40	79	20	79	40	80	20	69
5.	Isovanillin	40	79	70	68	70	75	31	98
6.	3-Benzyloxybenzaldehyde	50	85	100	85	35	72	20	70
7.	Benzyloxyvanillin	30	90	40	72	30	90	30	83
8.	Benzyloxyisovanillin	40	72	40	65	100	73	40	90

^aIsolated yields.

drazones using phosphorus pentoxide under microwave irradiation in solvent-free condition at ambient pressure (Scheme 1). Phosphorus pentoxide regenerates aldehyde within 20–120 s with the yield of 65–98% (Table 1). The reagent is inexpensive and easily available and widely applicable for the regeneration of aldehydes from their various derivatives³³. Using phosphorus pentoxide by conventional heating method, the reaction was still incomplete after 6 h³⁴. In the presence of phosphorus pentoxide by the conventional heating method, the oximes did not furnish any amide by Beckmann rearrangement³⁵. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report for regeneration of aldehydes from their derivatives using phosphorus pentoxide.

X = OH, NHCONH₂, NHPH, NHTs

Scheme 1

Experimental

IR spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR-RXI spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker AM 300L FT spectrometer (300 MHz). The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (BPL-Sanyo, BMO-700T, 2450 MHz, 1200 W).

General procedure : P₂O₅ (3 mmol, 423 mg) taken in a 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask was cooled to –10° for 15 min, then 2 drops of water were added to it. It was further cooled for the same period at that temperature and then mixed with the derivative of aldehyde (0.5 mmol, except for tosylhydrazone, which was taken in 0.33 mmol). Then the flask was placed in an alumina bath (heat sink) inside the microwave oven and irradiated for a specified time (Table 1). After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC), the product was extracted with ether (3 × 5 ml), washed with brine (5 ml) and dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the solvent afforded the product. When P₂O₅ was cooled to 0° at the initial stage, the yield was poor and if added to the aldehyde derivatives at RT, the mixture got charred before completion of the reaction. All the products were characterized by ¹H NMR spectroscopy and by comparison with IR spectra of the authentic samples.

In conclusion, we have developed a solvent-free method for the regeneration of aldehydes from their various derivatives using phosphorus pentoxide under microwave irradiation in short time.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi, and University of Calcutta, for providing financial support for this work.

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